

A nonperturbative quantum transition state theory of reaction dynamics using Path-integral Thermal Cluster Cumulant (PI-TCC) method

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Abstract : In this article, a nonperturbative path-integral quantum transition state (PI-QTST) theory is proposed for estimating quantum effect in reaction dynamics in which the rate of the reaction is successfully modelled as the crossing of quantum particle over the free barrier of the double-well potential. It is well known that the rate essentially depends on the centroid density $\rho(x_0^*)$ at the top of the barrier x_0^* dividing the two well representing the two stable configurations and x is defined along the reaction coordinate in one dimension. In path-integral approach to quantum transition state theory (PI-QTST), the quantum effect is estimated by calculating the ratio of the quantum grand partition function constrained to x_0^* , $Z_q(x_0^*)$ to its classical counterpart $Z_{cl}(x_0^*)$ and is called quantum correction factor, Γ . The quantum grand partition function $Z_q(x_0^*)$ is computed by using our non-perturbative Path-integral based Thermal Cluster Cumulant (PI-TCC) method. It is also shown that the value of quantum correction factor, Γ tends to unity as the temperature goes high indicating the validity of the theory.

Keywords : Reaction dynamics, classical transition state theory, classical transmission coefficient, quantum transition state theory, quantum correction factor, grand partition function, Path-integral Thermal Cluster Cumulant (PI-TCC) method, nonperturbative strategy.

1. Introduction

The paradigm describing the hopping of quantum particles (e.g. electrons, protons, molecules etc.) from one site to another is a common feature in Physics, Chemistry and Biology^{1,2}. Some of them are electron transfer reactions^{3,4}, proton transfer in polar solvent^{5,6}, diffusion of hydrogen in metals^{7,8}, etc. The study of these phenomena is relevant as it provides us with some information about the energetics and detailed mechanism of dynamical processes. Most of the hopping processes are accompanied by crossing a potential barrier. In other words, the quantum particles in these processes are as if crossing the potential barrier of a double-well. There is a vast literature in this field, but it is not possible to mention all of them. Let us mention a few of them. In the year 1935, Eyring⁹ developed the classical transition state theory (TST) where the rate of attaining the metastable transition state separating two stable equilibrium states is determined by the Boltzmann factor. Kramers¹⁰ developed the theoretical formalism for taking into account the effect of frictional forces on the barrier crossing of par-

ticle exhibiting Brownian motion. Yamamoto¹¹ and Miller^{12,13} made the theoretical developments where the rate constant is shown to be related to the flux-flux autocorrelation function. There are approaches¹⁴ where the flux-flux autocorrelation function is analytically continued to real-time. Wolynes¹⁵ evaluated the reactive-flux correlation function by means of a path-integral approach for the rate of barrier crossing by a quantum mechanical particle coupled to a heat-bath at finite temperature. This is the quantum analogue of Kramer's classical theory of the rate of activated events. Gillan¹⁶ formulated an imaginary-time quantum path-integral (PI) method that showed the barrier crossing rate is proportional to the probability of finding the quantum path-centroid at the barrier top. Geva *et al.*¹⁷ developed a path-integral based centroid molecular dynamics (PI-CMD) simulation method that calculates quantum mechanical reaction rate constant in terms of the position-flux correlation function. Following the ideas of Gillan, a rigorous path-integral quantum transition state (PI-QTST) theory was developed by Voth, Chandler and Miller¹⁸ for computing the thermal rate

constants for infrequent events that occurs in multidimensional quantum system. This procedure focuses on the equilibrium statistics of the centroids for the imaginary-time quantum paths and its analytical version was achieved by using variational principle. A Variational Transition State Theory (VTST) was developed by Truhlar *et al.*^{19,20} where the barrier position is optimized to get the minimum effective reactive flux over the barrier. Finally, an extensive review on Transition State Theory (TST) can be found in Ref. [21].

In the present paper, we have developed a nonperturbative PI-QTST to estimate the quantum effect on the barrier crossing phenomena in general of the quantum particles using our nonperturbative path-integral based thermal cluster cumulant (PI-TCC) method. The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we have reviewed the PI-TCC method. In Section 3, we have presented the basic concepts of Transition State Theory (TST). In Section 4, quantum correction factor, Γ is defined and its expression is derived by means of our PI-TCC method. In Section 5, the computed values of Γ at various temperatures, T for both the symmetric and the asymmetric double-well potentials are presented and explained. Finally, the paper is ended with the concluding remarks in Section 6.

2. Path-integral Thermal Cluster Cumulant (PI-TCC) method : A resume

The path-integral representation of the partition function Z_q in coordinate representation is given by^{22,23}

$$Z_q = \text{Tr} e^{-\beta H} = \int dx \langle x | e^{-\beta H} | x \rangle = \int dx U(x, -i\beta; x, 0) \quad (1)$$

where the position eigen-basis satisfies $\langle x | x' \rangle = \delta(x - x')$ and $\int dx |x\rangle\langle x| = 1$. Using Feynman's technique eq. (1) can be written as

$$Z_q = \oint D[x] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2(\tau) + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0^2 x^2(\tau) + V[x(\tau)] \right] d\tau \right) \quad (2)$$

where \oint denotes path-integration over all cyclical paths, $x(\tau)$ with imaginary-time variable $\tau = it$ denotes quantum paths periodic in β , $V[x(\tau)]$ is a polynomial in $x(\tau)$.

Let us consider the general hamiltonian, H for the double-well potential as

$$H = \frac{\dot{x}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0^2 x^2 + \epsilon x^2 + \lambda x^4 + \eta x + d = \frac{\dot{x}^2}{2} + V(x) \quad (3)$$

with the unperturbed frequency is equal to ω_0 and ϵ , λ , η , d are the coupling constants, and $V(x)$ is given by

$$V(x) = \epsilon x^2 + \lambda x^4 + \eta x + d \quad (4)$$

where ϵ is a negative quantity.

Let us define the unperturbed partition function, Z_{0q} as

$$Z_{0q} = \oint D[x] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2(\tau) + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0^2 x^2(\tau) \right] d\tau \right) \quad (5)$$

Then, we have Z_q/Z_{0q} as an average given by

$$\frac{Z_q}{Z_{0q}} = \left\langle \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta V[x(\tau)] d\tau \right) \right\rangle \quad (6)$$

where the average has to be interpreted as the ratio obtained from eqs. (2) and (5).

Let us express the cyclical path $x(\tau)$ as a Fourier series involving the Fourier components x_m :

$$x(\tau) = x_0 + y(\tau) = x_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (x_m e^{i\Omega_m \tau} + c.c.) = x_0 + y(\tau) \quad (7)$$

where $y(\tau)$ takes care of the quantum fluctuations around the centroid, x_0 given by

$$x_0 = \frac{1}{\beta} \int_0^\beta x(\tau) d\tau \quad (8)$$

where $\Omega_m = 2\pi m/\beta$ are the Matsubara frequencies.

Substituting eq. (7) in eq. (2), we have

$$Z_q = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 \exp(-\beta V(x_0)) \times \oint D[y] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + V(x_0 + y) - V(x_0) \right] d\tau \right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 \exp(-\beta V(x_0)) \times \zeta[x_0, y] \quad (9)$$

where $\zeta[x_0, y]$ is called the **perturbed quantum fluctua-**

tion component (fgpf) given by

$$\zeta[x_0, y] = \int D[y] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + V(x_0 + y) - V(x_0) \right] d\tau \right) \quad (10)$$

Let us define the **unperturbed zeroth-order ‘local’ gpf** for the fluctuation component (fgpf) as

$$\zeta_0[x_0, y] = \int D[y] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 \right] d\tau \right) \quad (11)$$

which is the harmonic part of $\zeta[x_0, y]$.

Then, the perturbed component $\zeta[x_0, y]$ can be written as

$$\zeta[x_0, y] = \int D[y] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\left(\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 \right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 + V(x_0 + y) - V(x_0) \right) \right] d\tau \right) \quad (12)$$

where $\omega_0(x_0)$ is the **‘local’ reference frequency**.

Then the ratio $\zeta[x_0, y]/\zeta_0[x_0, y]$ is given by

$$\frac{\zeta[x_0, y]}{\zeta_0[x_0, y]} = \left\langle \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[-\frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 + \sum_{l \neq 0} \frac{1}{l!} \frac{\partial^l V[x_0, y]}{\partial x^l} \Big|_{x_0} y^l \right] d\tau \right) \right\rangle_y = \left\langle \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta V_f[x_0, y(\tau)] d\tau \right) \right\rangle_y = \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y \quad (13)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle_y$ denotes average with respect to the PI measure of y , called y -average hereafter and $\omega_0(x_0)$ is the ‘local’ reference harmonic frequency for PI measure.

From eqs. (9) and (13), we have

$$Z_q = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 e^{-\beta V(x_0)} \times \zeta_0[x_0, y] \times \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 e^{-\beta V_{eff}[x_0, y]} \quad (14)$$

with

$$V_{eff}[x_0, y] = V(x_0) - \frac{1}{\beta} \ln \zeta_0[x_0, y] - \frac{1}{\beta} \ln \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y \quad (15)$$

It is to be noted that the argument ‘ y ’ in $V_{eff}[x_0, y]$, $\zeta[x_0, y]$, and $\zeta_0[x_0, y]$ indicates that the quantum contribution is embedded in the respective quantities.

One can in principle evaluate $\zeta[x_0, y]/\zeta_0[x_0, y] = \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y$ by means of cumulant expansion method²⁴, but being perturbative in nature it is not suitable for systems with strong perturbation because the results diverge. In order to overcome this difficulty, let us embark on to the nonperturbative access to $\zeta[x_0, y]/\zeta_0[x_0, y] = \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y$. The route to this process is outlined as follows. Let us consider y as field variables, split y as $(y_+ + y_-)$, define y -normal ordered products whose y -average with respect to PI-measure vanishes, define y -contractions with respect to y -average, derive a Wick-like expansion formula for $\langle T[y(\tau_1) y(\tau_2) \dots y(\tau_n)] \rangle_y$, and finally write $U(\tau)$ as $U_{m,n}(\tau)$ with ‘ m ’ number of y_+ and ‘ n ’ number of y_- variables in normal order. This leads us to the operator differential equation of the form

$$-\frac{\partial U_{m,n}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} = \sum_{pqkl} \left[(V_f[x_0, y(\tau)])_{p,q} U_{k,l}(\tau) \right]_{m,n} \quad (16)$$

where $(V_f[x_0, y(\tau)])_{p,q}$ has p number of y_+ and q number of y_- variables in normal order. $[\dots]_{m,n}$ denotes that the m, n component of the composite has to be taken, and “ $V_f[x_0, y]$ ” denotes quantum fluctuation potential.

Let us posit a y -normal ordered exponential ansatz for $U(\tau)$ given by

$$U(\tau) = \{ \exp(S_f + u_f) \}_y \quad (17)$$

where

$$S_f(\tau) = \sum_{m,n} S_{m,n}(\tau) \{ y_+^m y_-^n \}_y \quad (18)$$

$$\{ S_f^2(\tau) \} = \sum_{\substack{m1, n1 \\ m2, n2}} S_{m1, n1}(\tau) S_{m2, n2}(\tau) \{ y_+^{m1+m2} y_-^{n1+n2} \}_y \quad (19)$$

Eq. (17) denotes S_f is the operator part of $U(\tau)$; $u_f(\tau)$ is the purely number part.

Substituting eq. (17) in (16), we have

$$\frac{\partial S_{m,n}^{k,l}[x_0,\tau]}{\partial \tau} = \left[\overline{\{V_f[x_0,y(\tau)]\exp(S_f(\tau))\}}_y \right]_{m,n}^{k,l} \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_f[x_0,\tau]}{\partial \tau} = \overline{\{V_f[x_0,y(\tau)]\exp(S_f(\tau))\}}_y \quad (21)$$

where the right side of eq. (21) is the completely contracted component of $\langle V_f[x_0, y(\tau)] \exp(S_f(\tau)) \rangle$. Eqs. (20) and (21) are called **PI-TCC equations**^{26,27}.

The use of *y*-normal ordered exponential Ansatz in eq. (17) then reduced the ratio $\zeta[x_0, y]/\zeta_0[x_0, y]$ in eq. (13) to the form :

$$\frac{\zeta(x_0)}{\zeta_0(x_0)} = \exp(u_f[x_0, \beta]) = \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y$$

or,

$$u_f[x_0, \beta] = \ln \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y \quad (22)$$

where u_f depends on x_0 via the hamiltonian, appearing in the exponential of eq. (14), which depends on x_0 . Thus, having solved for $u_f[x_0, \beta]$, we can evaluate Z_q from eq. (14) with $V_{eff}(x_0)$ is given by

$$V_{eff}(x_0) = V(x_0) - \frac{1}{\beta} \ln \zeta_0(x_0) - \frac{1}{\beta} u_f[x_0, \beta] \quad (23)$$

Note that it is a nonperturbative theory of calculating the effective classical potential, $V_{eff}(x_0)$. Being nonperturbative in nature, our theory works well at relatively low temperature regime where the quantum fluctuation is quite high.

3. The basic concepts of transition state theory

The study of reaction dynamics essentially deals with the rate of change of atom(s)/molecule(s) in course of time from an initial state (called reactant(s), “**R**”) to a final state (called product(s), “**P**”). It is experimentally found that there exists an energy barrier and/or entropy factor while transition from the initial state to the final state. This dynamics is successfully modelled by a double-well potential as shown in Fig. 1. Along the reaction coordinate “*X*”, the ‘initial state’, ‘activated state’ and ‘final state’ are at the position x_a , x_b , and x_c respectively and the corresponding frequencies of the harmonic wells at these three positions are ω_a , ω_b , and ω_c respectively.

Fig. 1. Sketch of a typical double-well potential curve.

It is to be noted that at the barrier top position x_b the potential energy $U(x_b) = -(1/2)\omega_b^2 x_b^2$ that is an inverted harmonic potential with frequency $\omega'_b = i \omega_b$, an imaginary frequency. According to the Transition State Theory (TST), the rate constant, k^{TST} for such transition over the barrier as shown in Fig. 1 is given by

$$k^{TST} = \rho_b(x_0^*) \times \Phi_b(x_0^*) \quad (24)$$

where $\rho_b(x_0^*)$ is the probability of finding the reactant at the barrier top (*b* position) having classical centroid x_0^* dividing the two wells representing the two stable configurations/states, and $\Phi_b(x_0^*)$ represents the flux out of the barrier top.

This rate constant, k^{TST} of the rate of change of atomic/molecular processes can be calculated by solving the time-dependent Schrodinger equations for the nuclei under Born-Oppenheimer approximation as there is a clear separation of time scale of vibrational and electronic motion. The time-dependent Schrodinger equation for the nuclear degrees of freedom is given by

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi_v(R_n, t)}{\partial t} = [T_n + \epsilon_v(R_n)] \psi_v(R_n, t) \quad (25)$$

where T_n , $\psi_v(R_n, t)$ represent nuclear kinetic energy and wave function at position R_n at time t respectively and $\epsilon_v(R_n)$ represents the Potential Energy Surface (PES) obtainable by any electronic structure theory, e.g. SCF, MCSCF, DFT, CCM, etc. The formal solution to eq. (25) is given by

$$\psi_v(R_n[f], t) = U(R_n[f], t; R_n[i], 0) \psi_v(R_n[i], 0) \quad (26)$$

where the evolution operator U is given by

$$U(R_n[f], t; R_n[i], 0) = \langle R_n[f] | e^{-iHt} | R_n[i] \rangle \quad (27)$$

for transition from the initial position $R_n [i]$ to the final position $R_n [f]$.

From eq. (27), we have

$$U(R_n[i], -i\beta; R_n[i], 0) = \langle R_n[f] | e^{-\beta H} | R_n[i] \rangle \quad (28)$$

Now comparing eqs. (27) and (1) we obtain the equilibrium partition function, $Z(\beta)$ at a particular inverse temperature, β in terms of position eigen basis is given by

$$Z_q(\beta) = \int dx U(R_n[i], -i\beta; R_n[i], 0) \quad (29)$$

It is to be noted at this point that the study of equilibrium statistical mechanics is the same as doing quantum mechanics in imaginary-time with closed paths with an integration over the coordinate, x .

Let us define a dividing surface function, $f(x)$ at point(s) x on the surface so that the function satisfy the relation²⁵

$$f(x) = 0 \quad (30)$$

then the rate constant k according to classical Transition State Theory (TST) is given by

$$k_{cl}^{TST} = [Z_{cl}^R]^{-1} \times \int dp \int dx e^{-\beta H(p,x)} \times \delta[f(x)] \times F[p,x] \times \Theta[p, x] \quad (31)$$

where

$$Z_{cl}^R = \int dp \int dx e^{-\beta H(p,x)} = \int dp \int dx e^{-\beta[(p^2/2m) + V(x)]} = [2\pi m/\beta]^{1/2} \times \int dx e^{-\beta V(x)} \quad (32)$$

is the classical partition function of the reactant, and $F[p, x]$ is the flux given by

$$F[p, x] = \left[\frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{p}{m} \right] = [\nabla_x f(x) \cdot v] \quad (33)$$

which represents the normal component of the velocity, ' v ' towards the product, $\Theta[\nabla_x f(x) \cdot v]$ is the Heavyside function that ensures that a Transition State is going to be converted to product positively, and $\delta[f(x)]$ selects the point at which flux acts.

On the other hand, to formulate the quantum mechanical transition state theory (QTST) one needs to compute the path-integral based quantum partition function for the reactant Z_q^R given by

$$Z_q^R = \oint D[x(\tau)] e^{-\beta V_{eff}[x(\tau)]} \quad (34)$$

Thus going from the classical-TST to the quantum-TST apart from the factor " $[2\pi m/\beta]^{1/2}$ " arising from kinetic part of the hamiltonian, the classical potential energy $V(x)$ is replaced by an effective potential $V_{eff}[x(\tau)]$. Consequently, the exact rate constant can be written as

$$k^{exact} = \Gamma \times k_{cl}^{TST} \quad (35)$$

where Γ is the **quantum correction factor**.

4. Derivation of the expression of quantum correction factor, Γ using PI-TCC method

Let us derive the expression of quantum correction factor, Γ for a 1-d double-well potential as shown in Fig. 1 whose barrier-top position is x_0^* that divides the two wells representing two stable configurations. This centroid point (x_0^*) represents the bottleneck of the rate process along the reaction coordinate and the particle density at this point is given by

$$\rho(x_0^*) = \frac{Z_q(x_0^*)}{Z_q} \quad (36)$$

where

$$Z_q(x_0^*) = \oint D[x] \delta(x_0 - x_0^*) \times \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{1}{2}\dot{x}^2(\tau) + \frac{1}{2}\omega_0^2 x^2(\tau) + V[x(\tau)]\right] d\tau\right) \quad (37)$$

is the partition function constrained to the position, x_0^* . The corresponding free energy is given by

$$F_q(x_0^*) = -\kappa_B T \times \ln Z_q(x_0^*) \quad (38)$$

The quantum correction factor Γ at the centroid point x_0^* can be estimated by calculating the ratio of $Z_q(x_0^*)$ to its classical counter part $Z_{cl}(x_0^*)$ and is given by¹⁸

$$\Gamma = \frac{Z_q(x_0^*)}{Z_{cl}(x_0^*)} \quad (39)$$

Thus, the entire problem boils down to the evaluation of $Z_q(x_0^*)$ and $Z_{cl}(x_0^*)$.

The expression of $Z_{cl}(x_0)$ is given by

$$Z_{cl}(x_0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int dx_0 e^{-\beta V(x_0)} \quad (40)$$

Thus, $Z_{cl}(x_0^*)$ is given by

$$Z_{cl}(x_0^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \times e^{-\beta V(x_0^*)} \quad (41)$$

where $V(x_0^*)$ is evaluated by solving the equation

$$\frac{\partial V(x)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=x_0^*} = 0 \quad (42)$$

for x_0^* and plugging it in $V(x)$.

On the other hand, $Z_q(x_0^*)$ is evaluated by using our path-integral based thermal cluster cumulant (PI-TCC) method^{26,27} that started from the Feynman's path-integral representation^{22,23} for computing thermal trace of Boltzmann statistical operator, $e^{-\beta H}$.

Let us rewrite eq. (9) as

$$Z_q[x_0, y] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\beta V(x_0)} \times \oint D[y] \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta H_{fluc}(x_0, y) d\tau\right) \quad (43)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} H_{fluc}(x_0, y) &= \frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + [V(x_0 + y) - V(x_0)] \\ &= \frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + V_{fluc}(x_0, y) \\ &= \frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 y^2 + \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0, y) \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

with

$$\bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0, y) = V_{fluc}(x_0, y) - \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 y^2 \quad (45)$$

Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Z_q[x_0, y] &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \times \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_0 e^{-\beta V(x_0)} \\ &\times \oint D[y] \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 y^2\right] + \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0, y) d\tau\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \times \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_0 e^{-\beta V(x_0)} \\ &\times \oint D[y] \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 y^2\right] d\tau\right) \\ &\times \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0, y) d\tau\right) \right\rangle_y \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

Therefore, at the saddle point x_0^* along the reaction coordinate we obtain the expression $Z_q[x_0^*, y]$ as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_q[x_0^*, y] &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} e^{-\beta V(x_0^*)} \\ &\times \oint D[y] \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 y^2\right] d\tau\right) \\ &\times \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0^*, y) d\tau\right) \right\rangle_y \\ &= Z_{cl}(x_0^*) \times \oint D[y] \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 y^2\right] d\tau\right) \\ &\times \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0^*, y) d\tau\right) \right\rangle_y \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

that leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Z_q[x_0^*, y]}{Z_{cl}(x_0^*)} &= \Gamma = \oint D[y] \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 y^2\right] d\tau\right) \\ &\times \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0^*, y) d\tau\right) \right\rangle_y \\ &= \left[\frac{(\beta\omega/2)}{\sinh(\beta\omega/2)} \right] \times \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0^*, y) d\tau\right) \right\rangle_y \\ &= \Gamma_{har.} \times \Gamma_{anhar.} \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where on the one-hand $\Gamma_{har.}$ denotes the harmonic contribution to the quantum correction factor Γ and is given by

$$\Gamma_{har.} = \frac{(\beta\omega/2)}{\sinh(\beta\omega/2)} \quad (49)$$

which for parabolic barrier separating the reactant and the product regions at position x_b with barrier frequency ω_b becomes

$$\Gamma_{har.}^{pb} = \frac{(\beta\omega_b/2)}{\sinh(\beta\omega_b/2)} \quad (50)$$

which is in agreement with the exact results of Ref. [18]. On the other-hand, $\Gamma_{anhar.}$ denotes the anharmonic contribution to Γ and is given by

$$\Gamma_{anhar.} = \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta \bar{V}_{fluc}(x_0^*, y) d\tau\right) \right\rangle_y \quad (51)$$

Table 1. PI-TCC results of quantum correction factor, Γ for a symmetric and an asymmetric double-well potential with various values of ϵ, λ, η and d

ϵ, λ	T	Γ	$\epsilon, \lambda, \eta, d$	T	Γ
-0.6, 1.0	0.18	0.26386	-0.6, 1.0, -0.2, 0.4	0.18	0.08674
	0.20	0.33543		0.20	0.12070
	0.30	0.63415		0.30	0.33879
	0.40	0.80303		0.40	0.53059
	0.50	0.88957		0.50	0.66548
	0.60	0.93472		0.60	0.75580
	0.70	0.95945		0.70	0.81660
	0.80	0.97373		0.80	0.85845
	0.90	0.98237		0.90	0.88806
	1.00	0.98784		1.00	0.90958
	1.50	0.99755		1.50	0.96089
-2.0, 1.0	0.10	190.76800	-2.0, 1.0, 0.2, 0.0	0.10	221.63139
	0.15	3.60279		0.15	3.42336
	0.20	2.71571		0.20	2.60642
	0.25	2.30198		0.25	2.22746
	0.40	1.60373		0.40	1.57078
	0.45	1.49259		0.45	1.46809
	0.50	1.40823	0.50	1.39140	

which can be calculated under any level of approximation by methods like variational, ordinary perturbative expansion, perturbative cumulant expansion²⁷, path-integral based nonperturbative cluster cumulant²⁷, etc. In this paper, we have evaluated $\Gamma_{anhar.}$ by our path-integral based Thermal Cluster Cumulant (PI-TCC) method^{26,27}. The results are presented in the next section.

5. Results and discussion

The computed values of the quantum correction factor, Γ is presented in Table 1 for the various values of the coupling constants, $\epsilon, \lambda, \eta, d$ and the temperature, $T = 1/\beta$. It is observed that as $T \rightarrow \infty$, $\Gamma \rightarrow 1$, i.e. Γ resembles classical transmission coefficient, κ_{cl} defined as $\kappa_{cl} = [k_{cl}/k_{cl}^{TST}]$, where k_{cl} is the exact classical rate constant, and k_{cl}^{TST} is the estimated classical rate constant as per classical transition state theory. It is also found that for double well potential with a relatively shallow depth of the well (i) $\Gamma \rightarrow 1$ very closely, (ii) the rate of convergence depends remarkably on the symmetry and the depth of the double well potential, and (iii) the quantum effect is not so prominent. But, it is clear that for relatively high depth of the well (i) the approach of $\Gamma \rightarrow$

1 is not so close, and (ii) the quantum effect is very high. Moreover, the estimated value of Γ has no upper/lower bound as PI-TCC method is nonperturbative in nature.

6. Concluding Remarks

In continuation to the earlier paper Ref. [27], the efficacy of our path-integral based thermal cluster cumulant method (PI-TCC) method is utilized to derive first-time a nonperturbative expression for quantum correction factor usually defined in Quantum Transition State Theory (QTST) considering double-well potential as model system. We have introduced the nonperturbative field theoretic treatment for computing the effect of quantum fluctuation at the saddle point dividing the two stable equilibrium configurations of the reactant and the product. The quantum correction factor is evaluated at the barrier top as a product of the contribution from the harmonic part of the potential and an average of the anharmonic part with respect to the gaussian path-integral measure around the centroid variable x_0^* . The anharmonic contribution, $\Gamma_{anhar.}$, is evaluated in a nonperturbative PI-TCC method, but in principle this can also be evaluated by Kubo's perturbative cumulant expansion method. This exercise will be shown in the forthcoming paper.

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